

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

First recorded incidence of rice bugs in Manipur, India

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Surveys of insects in the major rice growing districts of Imphal, Thoubal, and Bishnupur covered 24 villages of Manipur Sep-Nov 1986. Four species of bugs were recorded for the first time during the milk stage of rice. Three belong to family Pentatomidae, and one to Coreidae (see figure). These bugs caused chaffy grains and discoloration, depending on time of appearance and intensity.

Four rice bugs found in Manipur, India, 1986. 1) *Dolycoris indicus* Stal: mild, active in Apr-Oct. 2) *Menida histrio* (Fabr.): mild, active in Jun-Oct. 3) *Scotinophara coarctata* (Fabr.): mild, active in Jul-Sep. 4) *Cletus signatus* (Walk.): severe, active in Apr-Oct. Nos. 1-3 are Pentatomidae, 4 is Coreidae.

The stink bug *Cletus signatus* was a major pest, with 10-40% infestation. In severe cases, 2-3 bugs/ 10 panicles

caused heavy rice yield losses. Other bug species were of minor importance, with 3 to 6% infestation. □

Predators of brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål (BPH) in ricefields of the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

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Predators of BPH in the Mekong Delta were sampled visually.

The predator complex and its populations were counted on the bunds of ricefields in sample areas of 1 m² with 3 replications at 7-d intervals.

Some species that had high populations were *Lycosa pseudoannulata*, *Tetragnatha nitens*, *T. javana*, *T. virescens*, *Paederus fuscipes*, *Clubiona japonicola*, *Ophionea indica*, *Zelotes* sp., *Callitrichia formosana* (Table 1). The remainder of the complex were sparse.

Wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata*, four jawed spider *Tetragnatha* sp., staphylinid beetle *Paederus fuscipes*, and carabid beetle *Ophionea indica* are four important predators of rice BPH found in the Mekong Delta.

Table 1. Predator complex of BPH in winter-spring and summer-autumn, Hau Giang, Vietnam, 1985.

Family	Species	Abundance
Salticidae	<i>Bianor</i>	++
	<i>Plexippus paykulli</i>	+
	<i>Phidippus</i> sp.	+
Sparassidae	<i>Heteropoda</i> sp.	+
	<i>Clubiona japonicola</i>	++
	<i>Clubiona</i> sp.	+
	<i>Lycosa pseudoannulata</i>	+++
Oxyopidae	<i>Oxyopes</i> sp.	+
Tetrtrithidae	<i>Tetragnatha japonica</i>	++
	<i>T. javana</i>	+++
	<i>T. mandibulata</i>	++
	<i>T. nitens</i>	+++
	<i>T. virescens</i>	+++
Micrylantidae	<i>Callitrichia formosana</i>	++
Staphylinidae	<i>Paederus fuscipes</i>	+++
Carabidae	<i>Ophionea indica</i>	++
Coccinellidae	<i>Verania discolor</i>	++
	<i>Coccinella repanda</i>	+
Miridae	<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>	++
Veliidae	<i>Microvelia</i> sp.	++
Agrocnemidae	<i>Agrocnemis</i> sp.	++

++++ = highly abundant, +++ = abundant, ++ = less abundant, + = scarce.

Their population dynamics were observed during four seasons 1982-84. The study used rice varieties IR36, IR46, IR48, Triveni, Utri Rajapan, and TN1 in a randomized block design with three replications. Twentyday-old seedlings were transplanted at 20-

× 20-cm spacing, fertilized with 100 kg N + 60 kg P₂O₅ + 30 kg K₂O/ha, and hand weeded. Predator populations were recorded at 5-d intervals on 1 m² per plot.

Wolf spider occurred throughout the crop cycle. The peak period was at